

Perception of Teachers and Mothers about Impact of Father Absence ...

Perception of Teachers and Mothers about Impact of Father Absence and Presence on the Truancy Behavior of Secondary School Students

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Abstract

A child is born innocent and if nurtured with tender care and attention, then grows in positive way. Physical, mental, moral and spiritual development of the children makes them capable of realizing fullest potential. On the contrary, harmful surroundings, negligence of basic needs, wrong company and other abuses may turn a child to a negative action like truancy. The present study was designed to analyze the impact of father's absence on truancy behavior of secondary school students. The major objectives of the present study were: i) to find out the views of teachers about the truancy behavior of secondary school students in father's absence. ii) to find out the views of teachers about the truancy behavior of secondary school students in father's presence. iii) to investigate the mother's views about the truancy of their children in father's absence. iv) to investigate the mother's views about the truancy of their children in father's presence. A sample of four hundred students was selected through convenient sampling. This group was further divided equally on the students whose fathers were present and absent from home. Data was collected from sample student's mothers and teachers through questionnaire. Data was analyzed through Chi-Square. Teachers and mothers opined that students showed more truancy behavior in the absence of father. The study may be helpful both for teachers and students to overcome the anti-social behavior to increase the academic performance at secondary level. The study may also beneficial to prepare positive members of the society. It is recommended that proper programs and campaigns be launched for mothers to highlight and realize the difficulties of truancy behaviors through media and social media. In-service training for teachers may be conducted to recognize and solve the truancy behavior of students. In this way teacher may able to solve the truancy behavior and solve problems.

Keywords: Father Absence, moral, spiritual development, Physical, mental, father's presence

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Introduction

Truancy behavior is one of the most important indicators of anti-social behavior. Truancy behavior affects different aspects of student life. This behavior minimizes not only a student's academic achievement but also their conduct and performance. The father's absence and presence also have a positive or negative impact on the truancy behavior of secondary school students. A father's presence insures monitoring and proper guidance for a child student who feels fear about the complaint against him. In the father's absence, the truancy behavior flourishes. Behavior is the manner in which a singular or a group acts in relation to communal, state, or national activities. The behaviour of a human being is totally based upon previous experiences, whether they were nourishing or infuriating. Behavior was also influenced by the type of upbringing (parents, institute, and community) one received (Monette, 2005).

Human social behavior is principally initiated by upbringing in the family, and then by the environment, together with education and supplementary parameters. Worthy and in-depth education is a significant part of human life. Philosophizing education means to sketch out, and if we are to hunt for a way to draw out the individual mind, we must first have some clear concept as to what the mind is like and of what type those faculties are, which are equally the object and way of education (Vinond, 2010). Adolescence is a period of human development between childhood and adulthood, as indicated by certain characteristics that affect both self and family equally. These juveniles cultivate good behaviors but in some circumstances they do not. Parents and relatives pointly shake adolescents' behavior. In contrast, the decreasing adolescent's ant-social behaviour is caused by the contribution of parents' attention. Poor behavior has significantly degraded the situation. The parental checking process tells us that where the parent is conscious and well-informed about child's activities, it reduces the ant-social behavior in children. Parental observing is a significant element of anti-social and threat behaviors. Low parental checking has been linked with teenage anti-social behaviors (Fosco, Stormshok, Dishion & Winter, 2012).

There are numerous school-related, home-related, and individual student-related determinants of truancy among students around the world. Truancy is a very dangerous delinquent behavior among students. This is because it can have a negative impact on their lives. Truancy interferes with student's education as it interferes with their concentration, ability to catch up, on and off-campus learning, which may result in difficulty in improving their academic achievement.

Statement of the Problem

Being a teacher, the researcher observed anti-social behaviors create disturbance in the peaceful educational environment of school. The suggested study was on the impact of father's absence on the truancy of secondary school students.

Objectives of the Study

The major objectives of the present study were:

- i) To find out the views of teachers about the truancy behavior of secondary school students in father's absence.
- ii) To find out the views of teachers about the truancy behavior of secondary school students in father's presence.
- iii) To investigate the mother's views about the truancy of their children in father's

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absence.

iv) To investigate the mother’s views about the truancy of their children in father’s presence.

Hypotheses of the Study

To achieve these objectives, the null hypotheses was framed:

H1: There is no significant impact on the truancy behavior of secondary school students in father’s absence in views teachers.

H2: There is no significant impact on the truancy behavior of secondary school students in father’s presence in views of teachers

H3: There is no significant impact on the truancy behavior of secondary school students in father’s absence in views of mothers.

H4: There is no significant impact on the truancy behavior of secondary school students in father’s presence in views of mothers

Significance of the Study

The study is important to find out the anti-social behavior of the student at secondary level in Pakistan. The study may be helpful both for teachers and students to overcome the anti-social behavior to increase the academic performance at secondary level. The study may also beneficial to prepare positive members of the society.

Review of Related Literature

The behaviour of a student plays an important role in increasing the academic performance of student. The truancy behavior of a student can badly affect their academic performance. In the social sciences, which comprise sociology, economics, psychology, and anthropology, human behavior is studied. Behaviors change all through a person’s life, as he/she progresses from first to last stages of life, for instance, childhood, adolescence, parenthood, and old age. Human behavior is shaped by circumstances and psychological qualities (Wikipedia 2019). To examine and evaluate the behavior, it has been divided into different classes. Human behavior classification is given below:

Observing others gives one an idea of how new behaviours are performed, and this coded information later serves as a guide for action (Bandura, 1978). Learning theory of Albert

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Bandura is one of the several models which have been offered. It has an exceptional place in the standard of theories about human behavior and learning. He presented the theory that all learning is the outcome of observing and modeling the manners of others.

Antisocial behavior is deliberated by different social scientists, each of which has its own perception of the explanation and dimension of what is antisocial. In contrast to pro-social behavior, which involves behaviour that helps or benefits society, anti-social behaviour is self-centered behaviour that violates social customs, lacks courtesy for others, and may cause harm to society, whether intentional or through inattention. It also means performing in a way that is likely to cause hurt to one or more in-home groups. To be anti-social, behavior must be determined to the point of also causing harm or uneasiness in the environment. Anti-social behavior may include destructive behaviour, using offensive words, insulting or rude language, bullying, hostility, beating, and theft (Chinelo & Igbashal, Moses & Chiahemba 2010).

Student's anti disciplinary behaviors such as troublemaking talking, constant dodging of work, joking, inquisitive with teaching activities, harassing class fellows, verbal abuse, rudeness to teacher and mates, disobedience, aggression, bullying truancy practicing from rare to frequent, mild to exact, is a problematic issue in everyday school (Johnson & Fullwood, 2006). Truancy can be explained as the determined unexcused denial of a student to go to school in rebelliousness of parental power and in violation of an appropriate obligatory school attendance law (Abrams & Ramsey 2003). Truancy is running away from the classes or school with no sanction of school administration. And it is a habit to stay away from classes and school without saying no to pass up work load like assignment, test, evaluation and other curricular tasks. Moreover truancy is staying away from school within school time without any permission of parents and school with a vision to avoid, punish, escaping particular activities and avoiding certain endorsed school tasks (Unkanyirioha, 2003).

Truancy is one of the never-ending dilemmas in schools. The problem is becoming critical for parties day by day. This is why students in school are the birthright of future generations. The behavior of truant is based on many reasons. It may be students' inside factors, socioeconomic position, and the environment of the culture. Students are the next generation that plays a vital role in raising the nation. For that reason, the Ministry has implied "Professional Circular No.6/1995: Handling the Problem of Truancy" states the information on student disciplinary issues shows that truancy is the chief and most common disciplinary issue that happens among students. It is said that truancy is aiming for a "Zero Defect" in disciplinary issues in school because if the problems do not find their own way out, they will twist out to be shoddier. Truancy is a penalizing act that breaks the rules of the school, and if it is left untouched, it can have a negative influence on the students, the school, the family, and the nation because the students are the way of ensuring the progress of the country. This disciplinary action may cause the students to lose their self-esteem, raise the habit of irresponsibility in their studies, and it will also direct them to engage in other harmful social issues such as drug addiction and loitering. The phenomenon of truancy is spreading among students. In the meantime, the problem of truancy does not only engage the institution but also has an attraction in the mass media (Abdullah and chong 2010).

Sheldon (2007) shows that truancy and absence are connected with a display of negative

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students and outcomes such as low academic achievement, fewer school attachments, delinquency, sexual promiscuity, drug use, and school withdrawal. The association of truancy to school withdrawal is well recognized whereby truancy involvement is sometimes called "drop-out prevention." The troubles of truant students are likely to carry on into adulthood, raising the possibility of criminality, drug addiction, matrimonial problems, violence, low-status professions, unsound careers, and unemployment (Halfors, Veveera, Iritam, Khatapoush & Saxe, 2002).

Factors of Truancy

The complex interaction of truancy correlates diagonally with these four domains, which has led to the development of truancy interventions. Generally, these interventions have addressed the causative factors specific to each of the four domains and have been classified consequently as:

(Teasley, 2004)

- Individual factors include learning disabilities, school phobia, low school attachments, and behavior issues.
- Family factors connected to truancy include low financial status, single-parent, maltreatment of child, parental disabilities, lack of parental participation in education, and family mobility.
- School factors include inconsistency interaction with teachers, poor attendance policies, no-accommodation of different learning styles and harassment
- Community factors linked with truancy are mostly associated to the correlation between less family income, locality residence, and restricted schools. These soundings are marked by superior levels of family mobility, hostility, maltreatment, offense, drug use, and joblessness that taken together contribute to more truancy (Teasley, 2004).

Richard and Sutphen (2010) discovered a fifth class called "multimodal interventions" that is the combination of interventions from the four Teasley domains. These classes of truancy interventions organize the most general methods that originate in the literature to tackle the problem. It is intentional to support social work researchers and practitioners to analysis the literature with the objective of providing guidelines for best practise and tracking for further

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research.

Iheanyi and Okwakpam (2012) concluded that there is an important difference between family circumstantial and student factors. The inference of this is that the student's family background effects the student's truancy level greatly. Findings of this study stated that truancy is damaging to students' achievement, development, promotion, self-respect, and employment prospects. Obviously, students who skip school fall behind in the classroom. This leads to low self-respect or regard, and there might be a risk that students will be struck out of school. Truancy of students is a bad behavior that expends much more after school than the school. It disturbs the students, the family, the school, and the community at large. The student him/herself, family context, the school, and the community are contributing factors to the reasons for the truancy of students at secondary schools.

Qaiser (2017) study found that electronic media contributes to the most powerful factors of truancy. The contributory factors of students' truancy are family background, quarrels of parents, lack of attention by parents, illiteracy, parents' death, poverty, divorce, and deficient services at home. Melissa (2009) findings revealed that electronic media factors are the most influential factors contributing to truancy. Furthermore, family background factors, students' factors, peer group factors, and school environment factors were also found to be contributory to students' truancy. On the other hand, teacher factors were found to be the least contributory factors to students' truancy. As discussed in this article, Maduabuchi (2009) established that truancy exists among secondary school students in our society. This ugly incident carries with it numerous devastating effects on the truants and society at large. Society should see truancy as one of the greatest hindrances to the achievement of functional education for values and knowledge skills for national development. Abdullah, Ismail & Najaatu (2017) investigated that except attitude of teachers, peer influence contributes to truancy. Peer influence is seen as the most dominant factor. Previous research addressed the different factors of truancy. The present study focused on the absence and presence of a father at home.

Research Methodology

In present study following research methodology was adopted.

Population

The target population for the study was consisted of 1, 80,542 students, 7748 teachers of Punjab public High schools. (Govt. of Punjab, 2019).And mothers of all these students were included in the study.

Sample

A sample of four hundred students was selected through convenient sampling. This group was further divided equally between the students whose fathers were present at home and whose fathers were abroad. Data was collected through selected students' teachers and mothers'. One hundred and eighty-six (186) teachers were selected who had been teaching grade X for at least two years. Two hundred forty-four (244) mothers of sample students were selected who were educated and volunteer to give responses. The education criteria for mothers were set at a minimum of matriculated so that they could perceive the purpose of

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the research and respond to the items of the questionnaire easily.

Research Instruments

. The five-point scale, also known as Likert Scales considered being the most suitable for obtaining data on human behavior and attitudes (Farooq & Tabassum). Questionnaire was prepared on these scales.

5	4	3	2	1
Often	Some times	No reply	Rarely	Never

Validity of the Instrument

The researcher developed a close-ended and open-ended questionnaire (five point Lickert Scale (having five options: sometimes, often, no reply, rarely, and never) for this research in light of already available literature. Maria, Molero, and Martinez (2017) conducted research on antisocial behaviour and interpersonal values in high school students, and antisocial behaviours were mentioned in the questionnaire. Researchers changed the ant-social behavior item in a demographic situation. The developed questionnaire was validated with expert opinion. The questionnaire was viewed by a sociologist, Nimra Asif, who is working with an NGO that is working on teen delinquency. A physiologist who is running a counseling center for children reviewed the items for anti-social behaviour students. The higher secondary school subject specialist in psychology, Rizwana Malik, established a counseling center for students at school to prevent the anti-social habits of students. She read the questionnaire and agreed that the questionnaire shows the same anti-social habits that she faced at school. Then it was reliability checked before it was administered to the sample.

Reliability of the Instrument

Cronbach’s Alpha. Cronbach’s Alpha of items was used to measure the reliability of questionnaire the formula of Cronbach alpha is: $\hat{\alpha} = \frac{N \cdot \bar{c}}{\bar{v} + (N-1) \cdot \bar{c}}$ The formula of Cronbach alpha is defined as

Where N = the number of items.

$\bar{c}$ = average covariance between item-pairs.

$\bar{v}$ = average variance. (Lavrakas, 2008).

The calculated value of reliability of the teacher’s questionnaire was 0.870 and for mothers questionnaire it was 0.800. It shows that both questionnaires reliability was good.

The present study deals to analysis the impact of fathers absences on the truancy behavior of secondary school students.to find out the impact of fathers absence on the behavior of student, data were collected from teachers and mothers of sample students. Mean and Standard deviation were calculated through SPSS. Chi-square was used to analyze the impact of father’s absence and presence on the student’s behavior and performance.

Table 1: Cumulative Score of Truancy Students in the Absence of Father In views of Teacher

Total	M	SD	χ^2	P value
86	26.407	10.410	74.000	.000

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df=25χ²at 0.05=30.14

The above table shows the cumulative score of truancy in views teachers regarding the absence of father. The χ² tabulated value was 30.14 while the calculated value was 74.0 which was higher than tabulated value. There was significant difference between these values. Thus the null hypothesis was rejected. It means that there was a significant impact of father's absence on the truancy behavior of secondary school students.

Table 2: *Cumulative Score of Truancy Behavior of Students in the Presence of Father in views of Teacher*

Total	M	SD	χ ²	P value
86	23.104	10.600	89.349	.000

df=25χ²at 0.05=38.89

The above table shows the cumulative score of truancy behavior in views teachers regarding the presences of father. The χ² tabulated value was 38.89 while the calculated value was 89.34 which were higher than tabulated value. There was significant difference between these values. Thus the null hypothesis was rejected. It means that there was a significant impact of father's presence on the truancy bullying behavior secondary school students.

Table 3: *Cumulative Score of Truancy of Students in the Absence of Father in views of Mothers*

N	M	SD	χ ²	P value
118	25.466	10.476	130.983	.000

df=25χ²at 0.05= 38.89

The above table shows the cumulative score of the truancy in views of mothers regarding the absence of father. The χ² tabulated value was 38.89 while the calculated value was 130.98 which were higher than tabulated value. There was significant difference between these values. Thus the null hypothesis was rejected It shows that there was a significant impact of father's absence on the truancy behavior of secondary school students.

Table 4: *Cumulative Score of Truancy of Students In The Presence Of Father in Views of Mothers*

N	M	SD	χ ²	P value
126	22.349	10.540	53.524	.000

df=25χ²at 0.05= 43.77

The above table reflects the cumulative score of the truancy as per mothers in the presence of father. The χ² tabulated value was 43.77 while the calculated value was 53.52 which was higher than tabulated value. There was significant difference between these values. Thus the null hypothesis was rejected It shows that there was a significant impact of father's presence on the truancy behavior of secondary school student

Conclusion

The teacher's perception showed that there was a significant impact of the father's absence on the truancy behavior of secondary school students. The teacher's perception showed that

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there was a significant impact of father's presence on the truancy behavior of secondary school students. The mother's perception showed that there was a significant impact of father's absence on the truancy behavior of secondary school students. The mother's perception showed that there was a significant impact of father's presence on the truancy behavior of secondary school student.

Recommendations

In the study, teachers and mothers perceived that there was a significant impact of father absence on the truancy behavior of secondary school students. It is, therefore, recommended that proper programs and campaigns be launched for mothers to highlight and realize the difficulties of these anti-social behaviors through media and social media. In-service training for teachers may be conducted to recognize and solve the anti-social behavior of students. In this way, the teacher may be able to solve the truancy behavior and solve problems. Rationally, the students' performance may increase. For the emotional and social development of children, teachers may establish committees with the responsibility of social adjustment guidance.

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